

MARRIED LIFE AND CHILD ISSUE OF LEGITIMACY ON OBOLO LAND

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Abstract

The family unit is the bedrock of any society. Unfortunately, this unit is being attacked from within and without by problems like divorce, illegitimate children and widowhood rites which are rocking the very foundation upon which the society is built. The thrust of this work which is on the Obolo (Andoni) people seeks to examine the relationship between the marital status of a woman and the legitimacy it confers on her Obolo born child. In other words it seeks to answer the following questions: are there truly illegitimate children in Obolo land? How has Obolo customs and tradition treated the problem of illegitimate children over time? What prospects exist for such children in Obolo land? Recommendations were made on how to ameliorate these problems.

Key Words: *Obolo land, Andoni, legitimacy, Marital Status,*

Introduction

The issue of illegitimate children is one that cannot be wished away because we are in modern democratic times, and neither can it be assumed as inconsequential as it is embedded in the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 as amended (Section 42 (2) CFRN 1999).

Illegitimate children and the problems associated with them have been with us from time immemorial. In the Bible we were confronted with the stories of Ishmael the son born to Abraham and Hagar (the maid of Sarah, his wife) and Japheth the son of Gilead by an harlot; the

attendant conflicts that arose in both situations and how they were resolved by God and the people concerned are reproduced in Genesis 21:8-21 and Judges 11:1-12 (Holy Bible, KJV 2004) Illegitimate children are the product of moral decadence in our society. In America it was discovered that this set of children are born as a result of the following five (5) conditions:

- i. a decrease in the birth rate of women who are married;
- ii. a decline in the portion of women of child bearing age who are married;
- iii. an increase in the birth-rate of non-married women;
- iv. a decline in marriage among young adults and;
- v. increase in sexual activity (Robert 1999:1-3). In Nigeria on the other hand, children are born out –of-wedlock as a matter of choice in most cases by men and women who are seeking for children and/or pleasure or by couples who at times are encouraged by traditions.

Robert (1999:1-3) goes on to state that since 1945 there has been an increase in the birth rate of children born out-of-wedlock from 125,000 in 1946 to 1.26million in 1999. As if these figures are not startling enough, he further revealed that the issue of illegitimate children is not peculiar to any particular race in America but prevalent among whites and coloured. Highest on the ladder, according to him, are whites followed by blacks and at the bottom of the ladder are Asians /Pacific Islanders.

If these revelations about “out –of-wedlock” children in an American society, where records are properly kept is startling, let us for a moment think about our country, Nigeria, where statistics are almost always inflated, “deflated” or “under flated” – what it will be like. If America is worried about this trend, what should our attitude and concern be especially now that it is clear that there is problem on our hands, a problem that is created not out of necessity but because we cannot control our Libido?

Sequel to the above, this paper intends to study the situation among the *Obolo (Andoni)* people of Nigeria and to establish if truly there are illegitimate children in *Obolo* land, how the *Obolo* customs and tradition has treated the problem of illegitimate children over time and what prospects exist for such children in *Obolo*-land. In doing this selected relevant literature will be

reviewed in addition to oral traditions collected through interviews; finally a general overview of *Obolo* position will be given, and conclusions drawn from there.

Literature Review

The issue of the legitimacy or illegitimacy of a child arises mainly when there is a resource(s) to contend for and which the birth circumstances of the child serves as a title to that claim. It is in this title to claim that discrimination arises, and in order to protect innocent children from being victimized, discriminated against or denied their rights out rightly by mere reasons that they were born by parents who were not lawfully wedded by ordinance of tradition; laws are enacted to checkmate such actions. Section 42(2) constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) provides that:

No citizen of Nigeria shall be subjected to any disability or deprivation merely by reason of the circumstances of his birth.

While supporting this stand of the constitution in *Agbai V. Okagbue* (1991) 7 NWLR, (Pt 204) 391Sc, Wali JSC (as he then was) opined that any customary law that sanctions the breach of an aspect of the rule of law as contained in the fundamental human rights provision guaranteed to a Nigerian in the constitution is barbaric and should not be enforced by our courts.

Akande (2000:105), quoting the 1999 Constitution Drafting Committee Report, said that the original draft of the committee specifically stated that “no citizen of Nigeria shall be subject to discrimination merely on the ground that he was born out of wedlock. According to her, the objection to this position under the 1999 constitution is that it is repugnant to morality. Citing the case of *Salubi V. Nwariaku* (1997) 9 NWLR (Pt. 504) 442 CA, she noted that it would appear that any law or act whatsoever which encourages such discrimination today will not be consistent with the constitution. Unfortunately, the *Sharia* law which is operative in some parts of Northern Nigeria denies the “illegitimate” child any right to share in this father’s wealth (Akande 2000:105).

From the foregoing, it is clear that by making such provision in the 1999 constitution, the drafters of the document tacitly acknowledges the fact that the “illegitimate” child exists and will continue to exist and no amount of legislation can change the circumstances of birth, no legislation can make illegality legal, neither can it make a marriage that has not met the condition set down by law and traditions to become legal.

Illegitimate Child and the Obolo land

Our focus in this paper as earlier stated is to ascertain if truly illegitimate children exist in *Obolo* land; to find out how the *Obolo* custom and traditions has treated the problem; and the prospects that such children have in contemporary society.

The *Obolo* people are found in *Andoni* local government area of Rivers State and Eastern-*Obolo* local government area of Akwa-Ibom State, Nigeria. They are a people with beautiful customs and traditions that have lasted centuries (Ejituwu, 1991:1). These customs are meant to bring order and sanity to the communities. Traditions and customs regarding the illegitimate child are present till date cutting across the five (5) clans of *Obolo*-viz-Ngo, Ataba, Unyeada, Asarama (Rivers State) and Okoro etc (in Akwa-Ibom State).

Late C.G. Ene (Justice as he then was) in *Fiberesima*, (1999:141) stated that:

There is nothing like illegitimate children in *Andoni*, once a man agrees that the child is his, that child is entitled to other benefits and amenities which his other brothers and sisters would get from their father and relations.

With due respect to the Honourable Justice, this view if taken at face value will give the impression that the *Obolo* people have no regard to marriage and inheritance laws and this is not a very true position.

In *Obolo*-land nobody brands another person an unsolicited name; therefore, no one is called an “illegitimate child” (*Gwon Ugan*) under normal circumstances. It is not even used when people quarrel. This does not however mean that it does not exist. When there is something to share in the family bordering on inheritance the issue crops up.

In a polygamous home, inheritance is shared according to the number of wives and children sheared by them (*me owot-me-owot*) and not by the total number of children. In a

monogamous home on the other hand, inheritance is given to all the children (male and female alike) one has with his wife and anyone born outside whom the father has claimed.

Separate interviews conducted across the five clans of *Obolo* revealed that “illegitimate” children (*Bon/Gwon Ugan*) have existed in *Obolo* right from the olden days. According to Chief C.J. Enereujama, Nkpan –Akong (JP), an illegitimate child (*Gwon-ugan*) in *Obolo* land is that child that was born by a woman who was not married by the father of the child either through traditional marriage rite or the English marriage rite. The early *Obolo* people were matrilineal (Ejituwu 1997:130). Because of the high premium placed on the female child as builders of families, fathers have been known to give out their daughters to men who will father children that will eventually belong to their mother’s father (Ejituwu, 1991:130). Incidentally, according to him, the times have changed and the *Obolo* people are now patrilineal.

Chief J.J. Irikana, when interviewed confirmed that illegitimate children (*Bon-Ugan*) have been part of the *Obolo* society and system. According to him, the *Obolos* hold strongly to proper marriages among its citizens with an unwritten code of conduct guiding it and as many as disregard this code and procreate children without it are humiliated, hence the ownership of such children by their mother’s family and the denial of bride price (*Ikpoko Ibot*) to their supposed father.

In confirming the above position, Mr. Sylvarious Igbiapu explained that there are three (3) types of “illegitimate” (*Gun-Ugan*) children in *Obolo*-land: (i) one that the father is not known; (ii) one that the father has acknowledged being responsible for the pregnancy and has paid some damages (*Ikpoko-Ino*) but there is no marriage agreement between the couple; and (iii) one that is born by two different married couples. He explained further that in type i above, the child will belong to his mother’s family entirely with all the rights of the family accorded to him or her.

Type ii where the father acknowledges ownership based on the fact that whatever damage that has been paid does not mean part-payment in a marriage procedure, the child belongs to his mother’s family and will enjoy all rights of the family. He or she also enjoys the rights from his father’s family too. If a girl-child, at the ripe age of marriage, the mother’s family gives her out

in marriage. Being a biological father is not enough to sit over a daughter's marriage ceremony if you have not married her mother (even though you may have footed her education bills or feeding), but where there is understanding the money is shared between the two families. In the case of a boy, he will inherit anything, including chieftaincy titles in his mother's house. His father can give him inheritance but his father's family may not give him any entitlement until the traditional rites of claim has been met by the father.

On type iii, a child born by a married woman to another married man. The husband of the woman may give the child to the biological father if so desires. In most cases the child remains in his mother's husband's house without any form of discrimination. All that has been said goes to prove that there are illegitimate children in *Obolo*. If it were not so, men would have been taking their children home from the streets as of right.

Obolo Tradition and Custom regarding the illegitimate child

The *Obolo* people are a people who hold strongly to family ties. Children, whether born within or outside of marriage, are seen as human beings and therefore owned by the community generally (hence when a child greets an elder the response is always "yes, my child"). Issues of discipline and care are not left to the biological parents alone. According to Chief G.A. Johnson Aban-ile, a child born out of wedlock is placed in a position of envy by the mother's family members as he or she is pampered by all and protected by all. He is the son of all in the mother's family to the point that he/she may not feel the need for a real father as it is available to him in abundance. He is accommodated to the point that he inherits in his mother's family all that the family has to offer- including chieftaincy titles.

On the other hand, he went further to explain that the biological father loses all his right of ownership of the child and in the event of the child bearing a girl, he cannot take her pride price (*Ikpoko –Ibot*) or give her out in marriage in his own house among his brethren without the knowledge and consent of the mother's family. This sanction is embedded in the custom of the people and is common knowledge.

Despite the fact that the “illegitimate” child in *Obolo* is better placed and not directly discriminated against, yet the times are changing fast; education and modernization has taken hold of the citizenry and *Andoni (Obolo)* is no exception and people are no longer contented to dwell within the status quo. This situation has created problems for the illegitimate child in *Obolo* land.

Problems and Prospects of Illegitimate Children in *Obolo* land

In *Obolo* though the illegitimate child cannot be said to be a problem to the larger society, yet there exists problems relating to her. Firstly, issue leading to the family of the woman suing the man and his family- if the case is amicably resolved, then all is well, but if not there always exists animosity between the members of both families.

Secondly, most times the financial burden of the illegitimate child’s upbringing and training rests on the family of the mother; surely not all such children can receive quality education under this circumstance. Thirdly, there can be internal wrangling within the mother’s family as in most cases these children are preferred above those born by males of the house.

In her contribution, Mrs. Umaro Ebirien maintained that the illegitimate child may not directly be the problem but the mother- it is the mother who will go to the father to make demands. This in some cases has led to the breakdown of the family (divorce) as the wife in the house may not accept the child and may choose to leave the marriage.

Despite these problems, there is still a vista of hope for such children in *Obolo* Land. According to Chief (Dr.) J. Ubulom, much as the family of the mother of the child has every right and claim to the child, the father is given an opportunity to follow a proper traditional procedure to claim his child. The purpose of this is not marriage but to claim his right of ownership. However, if he and the woman agree to marry, then the proper marriage procedure is followed. According to him, to claim his child, the father and his family members will meet with the family of the woman for negotiations. At the end he pays whatever token he is asked to pay and both families share in drinks to seal the union. He noted further that the times are changing and that there are

instances where these children who have become adults and have been exposed to education and modernization have simply packed themselves to their biological father's house but this could not have happened in days gone by.

Conclusion:

The Obolo people are a people that hold strongly to high moral standard, family ties are not toyed with. In this work we have seen that the problem is not with the child but with the parents who could not control their libido. Consequently, in order to protect their society from degenerating into such an animalistic level where everybody is free to procreate without regard to laid down rules, customs and traditions, the Obolo people have built into their system societal values that not only protect the products of sexually uncontrolled desires (the illegitimate child) from abuse, neglect and discrimination but also sanctions the father who may want to hide behind porous legislations, education and modernization to shirk away from his responsibilities.

As has been echoed throughout this paper, times are changing and changes need to be made in our sexual and moral behaviour. It is recommended that legislation be made to draw attention from the effect to the cause(s) of immorality and moral decadence in our society. This it is believed will go a long way in curbing this scourge, then and only then can the problem of "illegitimate children" be solved.

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APPENDIX 1

Aban-Ile, Chief J.G. – Traditional Ruler and Lecturer.

Ebirien, Umaro Mrs. – Retired Chief Nursing Officer and Bishop's wife, Niger Delta Diocese

Enereujama, Chief C.J. – Traditional Ruler and Media Practitioner

Irikana, Chief J.J. - Traditional Ruler and Civil servant

Igbiapu, Sylvarius, - Retired Public Servant and Community Leader

Nkangwung, C.T. - Public Servant and activist

Ubulom, J. Chief (Dr) - Traditional Ruler and Lecturer.